

Survey paper towards the implementation of the loan management system

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Abstract

Loan management is an important aspect in most of the SACCOs as it enables it to secure its funds through managing them. This survey is carried out to determine the number of SACCO members that would be affected as a result of automation of the SACCO loan management system. It will show how gender, number of dependents, marital status, age bracket, use of computers and smartphones and other aspects influence loan acquisition at URA SACCO. During the exercise we used questionnaires and interviews as methods of data collection. We used informal interviews as we did not have specific questions or an interview guide. According to results obtained from the field over 90% of the results indicate that there is a need to automate the loan processes so as to widen their knowledge before acquiring a loan and to ease the loan acquisition process.

Keywords: SACCO, Cooperatives, Loan management, Microfinance, Village saving schemes.

1. Introduction

SACCOs (Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies) are predominant form of external financing for small and micro enterprises in most of the developing countries. Contemporary studies show that SACCOS' role towards developing these enterprises is increasing rapidly. According to the survey, only 14% of Ugandans are part of the formal banking sector, less than 10 million have bank account [1]. A study made by the bank of Uganda as far as financial inclusion is concerned shows that people access credit more from other financial institutions than in banks [2].

Despite the growth, SACCOs still face different challenges that include inadequate capitalization, poor leadership and governance, insufficient loanable funds due to poor management. The successful ones are due to the use of a good management information system [3].

For a SACCO to grow, there must be money that is generated from loans in which more members will be attracted to save and acquire more shares. This money must be properly managed using management

information systems. We reached out to two different urban centered SACCOs to justify the problems i.e. we visited the URA SACCO and the Overcomers' SACCO.

URA SACCO is at the URA Training School-Rotary Avenue Plot 40(Former Lugogo bypass). When any member to the SACCO requires a loan, he/she has to travel to the SACCO offices in order to pick or submit the application form. He/she has to return to the SACCO offices in order to check on the application progress.

The SACCO members are provided with the manual procedures in the process of acquiring a loan which seem to be time consuming and unsecure in terms of record keeping. The members have to first visit the SACCO offices in order to get an understanding of the SACCO processes and products which information can be provided online.

Currently, the SACCO uses a system that is only accessed by the SACCO staff and this system has less to do with loan management. It basically caters for savings and also does less of the analysis.

The SACCO is itself located in a small place that cannot accommodate the growing numbers of customers. The solution wouldn't be having another room but rather having some services provided online.

This survey was conducted to determine how URA SACCO handles and manages its loans. The study was designed to determine the number of members who may be affected as a result of automation of some SACCO processes.

2. Related work

SACCO is an acronym for Savings and Credit Cooperative Organizations. They are owned, governed and managed by their members who have the same common bond: they may be working for the same employer, belonging to the same church, labor union, social fraternity or living/working in the same community. A person admitted to membership in the SACCO after registration in accordance with the SACCO's by-laws.

A SACCO's membership is open to all who belong to the group, regardless of race, religion, color, creed, and gender or job status. It's a unique, democratic, member driven and self-help cooperative organization where members agree to save their money together and offer loans to each other at reasonable rates of interest. [4]

They face various challenges in their operations ranging from inadequate capitalization, poor leadership and governance to insufficient loanable funds due to poor management. They also face challenges issuing loans to members for example organization-procedural and structural challenges, communication challenges, Loan record challenges and many more. [5] They also experience issues like poor governance, limited transparency in management, Weak capital base and infrastructure weakness including ICT.

There are several types of Cooperatives and most focus on a particular economic sector, but others focus on the nature of membership. In essence, there are three broad categories of SACCOS: Community-based - SACCOS, Employee-based SACCOS and Agricultural SACCOS. [6]

Other forms of saving being undertaken in Uganda include the use of commercial

banks, Microfinance institutions, Village saving schemes, property, especially in land and real estate, livestock, in Roscas and Ascas (Rotational savings and credit Associations) and (Accumulated savings and credit Associations) and stocks or government bonds. [7]

3. Methodology and tools

In the process of data collection, we used the following tools:

- Interviews
- Questionnaires
- Observation

3.1 Interviews

Due to the busy schedule and the information that we needed, we decided to do some unstructured interviews. With interviews, it was very easy to collect a lot of information in a short time.

The main objectives for carrying out the interview were:

- To identify the need for system development
- To collect the functional requirements for the system
- To collect the non-functional requirements of the system

In efforts to establish the existence of the problem, we interviewed the following people:

- The manager at URA SACCO that helped us to understand what they go through in their day to day activities and showed us some of the challenges they face. He came up with an idea of developing a loan management system

as a module that they are highly ready to work with upon its success.

- Some of the members of URA SACCO that had less time to concentrate on the questionnaires that we had for them. They gave us a lot of information concerning what they go through to access SACCO services.
- The general manager at Overcomers' SACCO that uses one of the systems that has been developed i.e. Quest Banker and Akello Banker. We shared a lot from his experience with using the two systems. We used unstructured type of interview since much of the information that we intended to obtain from him was more private and he was at first hesitant to share some of the information with us.

3.2 Questionnaires

To the different employees and members, we had to use some questionnaires that are easy for people to feed in the information that is vital to them. In addition, questionnaires are more confidential than the interviews especially when it comes to sensitive information since information is provided anonymously.

The main objective for using the questionnaires was:

- To collect information to help in understanding the system user characteristics.
- To obtain crucial yet sensitive information from the SACCO members.

The first part consists of questions was related to the use of computer and the

second part consists of biographies and other questions related to the SACCO. A copy of the questionnaire is attached in Appendix.

Questionnaires were administered to both the employees of the SACCO and the members of the SACCO. Some of the members of the SACCO that received questionnaires include the employees at URA training school, URA-Kampala North, URA Liason office-Kololo and URA-Kampala South.

We printed 50 questionnaires and distributed them to the SACCO members and managers at different branches. Out of 50 questionnaires, only 47 were returned. Among the members who answered these questionnaires include Administrators, tax offices, accountants, Data clerks, SACCO supervisors, Auditors, Mobilisers and others.

A random, convenient sampling technique was used to collect primary data so as to avoid bias in the data. Each member of the research team was responsible for distributing questionnaires to members of the sample to different branches. To ensure confidentiality, respondents' names and contact details were kept anonymous.

3.3 Observation

Not all the information could be collected by just the questionnaires and interviews. We used observations to get to understand different issues.

We made some observations as far as SACCO operations were concerned at the times we were there. We observed how inconveniencing it is to manage some of the loans due to manual procedures involved in the process of acquiring a loan.

4. Results

According to the results over 90% of the population were influenced positively in regards to automation of the loan Management system. This means that members will take little time to apply for loans and monitor their repayment at any given moment in time.

Figure 1: Do members usually visit the internet?

Figure 2: Effect of automating the loan process

Figure 3: Willingness of members to apply for loans online

Yes- percentage of members willing to apply loans online
 No- percentage of members willing to apply loans manually.

The pie chart in figure 2 shows the number of members that are willing to apply for loans online and those who prefer manual process. According to the data collected from the field over 90% of members are willing to apply for loans online since it saves time and money which would have been spent in moving to SACCO offices.

Figure 4: Are members conversant with using web browsers?

According to the data collected from the field, 97.8% of the members are conversant with the usage of computers and smartphones. This means that our product targets the right population.

Figure 5: Do members have email addresses?

From the above bar graphs, most of the SACCO members have sufficient computer skills that will help them be able to use the SACCO system.

5. Discussion of the results

According to the results obtained from the field, its valid that members of the SACCO often visit the internet and are conversant with using different web browser such as chrome, Firefox, internet explorer which are potential supporters of our SACCO loan management system. This implies that most of these members shall find less difficulty in accessing and using our system.

According to the data collected from the field, 97.8% of the members are conversant with the usage of computers and smartphones. This means that our product targets the right population.

Previous research [7] indicates that many a time money is borrowed for agricultural use is instead diverted to other businesses and in some cases to solve family financial needs. We intend to develop a system that shall curb this and ensure loans acquired are put to their intended use.

Also value according to Zeithaml V [8] is the importance attached to services based on their usage and the amount paid in exchange. Quality on the other hand, is the meeting of the needs and expectation of customers. [9] is of the view that satisfaction is the meeting of the needs or wants of customers. Most customers and employees of the SACCOs are not satisfied with what is available and opt for change for example on the way services are delivered. Satisfaction is key to whether customers can come back for more services. [10]

6. Recommendation

According to the data generated from the field we recommend automating some SACCO processes as they save time and resources. The resources saved can be used by members to do other productive work that benefits them.

7. Conclusion

We call upon many SACCOs in Uganda to adopt to changing technology as it will enable them to increase efficiency of their processes and serve many customers. It will also enable them to manage member's information and keep manage of their records.

8. Future work

In our research, we concentrated on the loan services provided by the SACCOs yet we

ought to have looked at those offered by banks, microfinances and saving schemes among others.

Our future work is to do more research on the SACCOs so that we can have a loan management system module that can be used by different SACCOs to improve on their efficiency that will bring about many more customers.

We shall also identify more SACCO processes that need automation. This will save time and money of many members hence increasing on number of potential customers.

Many SACCOS lack technical skills and unreliable source of credit in case of deficit. This hinders the smooth operations of these SACCOS which leads to the following:

- Failing to deliver better and sustainable services to its members considering the stiff competition in the market.
- Loss of members, members' savings and shares caused by misuse of money and high rate of defaulters.
- Unable to produce financial report i.e. they normally operate without knowing their situations.
- Many SACCOS are too small and they cannot manage to employ qualified staff.

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